

EARTH SCIENCES

CLIMATE IS DISPERSION

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Abstract

The nature of global climate fluctuations is discussed. In contrast to the current view, the opinion is expressed that the main climate indicators are not average characteristics but their dispersion. Doubts are expressed that modern mathematical modeling of climate is capable of predicting its long-term evolution.

Keywords: Climate change, first moments of climate, dispersion of climate, ocean role in climate, mathematical modeling

The negative problems of global environment certainly do exist but they are created exclusively by the light-weighted and criminal activities of the civilization.

The initiation of the idea of global warming caused by increase of carbon dioxide emissions is usually attributed to the former US Vice President Gore. It's not fair. Back in the 70s of the last century, the Soviet meteorologist, director of the Main Geophysical Observatory M. I. Budyko began to promote this idea with great vigor. Once he made a report on this topic at the Presidium of the Academy of Sciences. After the report the president of the Academy of Sciences, Academician Alexandrov, who, among other things, was skeptical of the idea, asked how it would affect the climate of Moscow region (where he apparently had a "dacha"). "Oh, it's all right, - Mikhail Ivanovich replied, - it will get warmer in Moscow region to such extent that it might be even possible to grow bananas". "And what about the USA?" - the president asked.

It was not recommended to show sympathy to USA then, similar to nowadays, so Mikhail Ivanovich remarked that unfortunately, it would be worse in USA, i.e. the amount of precipitation would decrease, and the crops would become small. "For God's sake, Mikhail Ivanovich, where are we going to buy the grain then?" - The president asked. The scientist could not find what to reply to such a tactless and politically incorrect question.

At one of the presentations I asked Budyko how global warming will affect the dispersion of climate anomalies, i.e., the variability and spatial heterogeneity of the weather. He just glanced at a young scholar and found it unnecessary to give an explanation. This is that tactless question I am going to talk about now.

I used to do mathematical climate modeling with a rather imperfect model but I read and thought a lot about the climate problem. I still think it over now, although I am busy doing other things. I believe that now I can express my views in a more systematic way which does not claim to be a formal scientific description.

The main difficulty that arises in the study of climate is that the climate system is an infinitely complex thing, in the sense that it is highly nonlinear and multi-component. Different components are responsible for

different periods and intensity of the climate and weather fluctuations.

There is a significant difference between the concepts of climate and weather. When we look at the tap water flow, the climate of this process is, roughly speaking, the volume of the water flowing out for time unit. The weather of this process is the numerous, rapidly varying fluctuations of the water jet, the irregularities on its surface. Oddly enough, the weather forecast is a much better formulated problem than the climate forecast, and in a certain sense it is easier. To simplify the problem, we can say that the weather forecast is a deterministic task. The randomness that is not taken into account by the predictive model is partially eliminated by ensemble modeling, i.e. the multiple repetition of the forecast with the perturbed initial data and averaging over the ensemble. The initial conditions and the current state of the system are continuously corrected by a huge amount of the satellite, aerological and ground-based information. No matter how often people joke about it, we are definitely witnessing a dramatic improvement in the short-term weather forecast. A significant role here is played by a rapid increase in power of the computers, as well as the means of observation and communication.

The main obstacle to the increasing of the period of successful forecasting is instability, which manifests itself in uncertainty of development of the process at some points in time (bifurcation). Instability is a classic problem of mathematics, which manifests itself even in the branches of science that are far from mathematics - say, in history. If in 1917 the Russian Provisional Government had been more determined to suppress the Bolsheviks' activity simply by sending their leaders to kingdom come, the course of historical development of Russia and of the whole world as well would have been much more humane.

The inertial process is modeled comparatively accurately, but abrupt regime changes are difficult, if not impossible, to predict. Therefore, there is a natural limit of the deterministic weather forecasting that is unlikely to be ever overcome. This limit is in the range of about 10-15 days.

According to one of the most profound scientists in the field of geophysics – Prof. A. S. Monin, the primary definition of climate for a period of N years is an ordered set of weather conditions for the entire period. At first glance, this definition is non-constructive and tautological similar to the definition of the population as a set of individuals (however, the latter is not that stupid, but it is quite another story).

The entire weather ensemble appears too big, but in the statistical mechanics an ensemble of objects can be characterized with any accuracy by a set of integral characteristics, such as the average value, variance and high-order moments including multipoint moments, etc. Among them, the simplest is the zero moment, i.e. the volume average. The most popular among the followers of global warming is the simplest zero moment, i.e. the mean global temperature in the lower layer of atmosphere. We are not going to discuss how well this value is calculated (there are also many uncertainties here), but for now we assume that it is good. A much more important question is how well this characteristic characterizes the climate. This value comically resembles a classic indicator - the average temperature of the patients in hospital including the temperature of morgue inhabitants (in our case, the temperature in Antarctica). The variability range of temperature of all the hospital inhabitants (something around 40C) is so great that it makes no sense to talk about their average temperature with the accuracy of 0.1 C.

Once I was impressed by the sensitivity of atmosphere coupled with the ocean (in terms of distribution of its surface temperature) to small variations in the initial conditions and parameters of a model (taking into account the interaction with the surface, especially with the ocean, atmospheric radiation, cloud cover, etc.). The “success” in mathematical reproduction of climate is achieved as a result of intensive 'fitting' to what is known. In fact, the reliable climate modelling is actually non-existent now. The numerous calculations for as far as 100 years ahead are incredibly comical. If Earth were covered not by oceans but mostly by swamps or shallow lakes, the weather forecast and even climate would become much more deterministic, since the climate system in this case would not contain the inertial components; hence, the statistical regime would be much more uniform. The presence of the inertial component introduces new time modes and oscillations into the spectrum. In order to take them into account, it is necessary to include the blocks describing physics of the inertial component in a mathematical model. On Earth such a major component is the ocean, i.e. the reservoir characterized by enormous heat capacity and inertia. Unfortunately, reproducing the structure and evolution of the ocean is currently quite difficult. The reason for this is the poorly known physics of the connections between the surface and deep layers of the ocean, complicated by highly stable stratification. The ocean is mostly very cold: its depths are filled with water with a temperature of about 4-5 degrees. Isn't it amazing? At the same time, the lower layers of the ocean are even warmed by the geothermal heat. The upper layers of the ocean are on the average 10-20C warmer than the deep ones. The heat capacity of the

ocean is about 4 thousand times greater than the heat capacity of atmosphere. It is not difficult to understand that even the minor variations in the ocean temperatures can be accompanied by strong fluctuations in the temperatures of atmosphere. Since the ocean temperature anomalies are inhomogeneous in space, they generate strong inhomogeneity in temperatures and dynamics of atmosphere.

It is unlikely that someone can feel that the average annual air temperature has increased by 1-2 degrees. The warming by 1 degree is equivalent to moving by 100 kilometers towards the south (in the North hemisphere) - a big deal. However, many people notice that their weather has become much more diverse; in particular, the number of cases of dangerous phenomena has increased.

The tracing of changes in the average temperature reminds me of a recent result in wind wave climatology. It was calculated that high waves increased their height due to the global warming by one centimeter! A curious result, considering that high waves have a height of about 10 meters. Thus, it is assumed that the relative accuracy of this result is 0.1%, which, of course, is nonsense that does not deserve any discussion due to the extremely low accuracy of the information on sea waves. That example is very similar to the data on global warming.

The carbon dioxide is being mixed up all the time, its distribution being quite uniform. The temperature changes in space and time by dozens of degrees, while such fluctuations are accompanied by huge variations in all meteorological characteristics, so we have to assume that the climate system has the hidden mechanisms that transform a uniform effect into chaos. We hope that the adherents of global warming have already figured out how a weak forcing that is uniform in space and nearly constant in time can generate the local phenomena and high heterogeneity of the reaction of atmosphere. Apparently, their explanation is quite non-trivial, if it exists at all.

It is more logical to suggest that there are mechanisms directly causing the large-scale fluctuations; hence, the changes in the globally averaged temperature should be attributed to the residual effects occurring due to nonlinearity of the large-amplitude processes. The common sense says that climate is not really an average temperature, but rather, to a much greater extent, a set of states of atmosphere and ocean. The inter-annual and spatial variability in the Celsius scale is by 2 orders of magnitude higher than the very slow atmospheric trends which are not weather-forming in themselves. As compared with the huge fluctuations caused by the anomalies in distribution of heat inflows (for example, from the ocean) the effects of climate fluctuations in the average temperature can be considered as just a weak background. The global warming experts say: 'summer is hot, winter is warm' - this is a climate change due to carbon dioxide, and if both summer and winter are cold, then this is also due to the global warming, just the effect is more intricate (they are never confused). On top of it, according to the warmers the tropical cyclones depend on global temperature increase by 2 degrees, which even locusts can feel. As well as its

impact on frigidity and the number of sexual crimes committed by Catholic priests.

Recently the scientists have explored the future of the Gulf of Finland, of course, in the light of global warming. They hoped at first that it was the warming that caused appearance of some harmful seaweed. Then, to their disappointment, they found that the seaweed had been deposited on the bottoms of the ships arriving from the endmost lands. The climate can warm up by 2 degrees or cool down by 3, but it is not carbon dioxide that may destroy the human race, but the human stupidity. Sighing about climate change reminds of the panic once pushed about the deadly ozone hole which after a while was safely tightened and then reappeared again. Then it was realized that the ozone hole was just fluctuating. The climate sometimes boils, sometimes subsides, and it has always been so. There are reasons for such phenomenon but they are unknown, and no one really studies them. If we understand climate as a measure of the spatial and temporal variability of atmosphere, it is quite possible to assume that large climate changes can occur even if the global average surface temperature is completely constant. Since the measurements are extremely unevenly distributed, we can expect that the data with large variability reveal a significant residual trend in surface temperature, not to mention the fact that non-linearity itself can generate a zero mode.

A more natural assumption is that climate can be defined as a spatial and temporal dispersion, a statistical set of modes, rather than an average state which is poorly formulated and calculated and probably not representative. Until now meteorologists cannot explain the huge interannual variability of atmosphere. Otherwise, they would have learnt long ago to give a reliable background forecast for a period of more than one week, i.e., for one month, season and year. This success is, however, unnoticed, and it is due to its absence we are more suspicious of the results that are much simpler.

According to the warmers, global warming generates many local phenomena. For example, there are positive temperature anomalies in the Arctic basin, which is expressed in reduction of the area and thickness of ice cover. It is difficult to link that phenomenon directly with global warming. A more natural explanation is that the heat transported by the Gulf Stream has increased. Why? This is another question that is not easy to answer, since it requires some understanding of mechanics of the ocean circulation systems, including the ability to perform the detailed mathematical modeling of those systems, which is currently impossible. So this science has not developed beyond construction of speculative qualitative schemes.

Nevertheless, the most effective (and at the same time the most vulnerable) evidence of global warming due to carbon dioxide is provided by the numerical experiments with the global climate models. These models usually include the models of atmosphere, ocean and sometimes - continental ice. The atmospheric models are well designed for weather forecasting. The same cannot be said about the ocean models. The upper part

of the ocean (about 200-300 meters thick) is closely connected to atmosphere, but it is already hundreds of times more heat-containing than the atmosphere. These ocean layers are highly stratified, so their dynamics and vertical thermal conductivity are very complex, which gives rise to numerous speculations, none of which can be considered as well-founded. The thermal and other interactions with atmosphere are calculated with simple empirical formulas, which obviously cannot give the accuracy higher than 20%. The exchange of heat with the depths of the ocean is even more complex. There are opinions that the filling of the ocean with cold water occurs in the narrow zones and at certain season phases. The physics and intensity of this process is definitely unknown.

Let's consider a good model of atmosphere and instead of the ocean, add to it, say ... a slightly overgrown pond with the ocean outlines, a few meters deep. A pond can warm up, cool down or even freezes over, but it is understandably limited in its ability to create the heat content anomalies and transfer heat from one place to another. With such a simplified climate system we could calculate the evolution of the Earth's climate, for example, for one hundred or even one thousand years. The analysis of the results would reveal no special surprises in such system: the weather would be more or less steady, of course with the cyclones and anticyclones though with no particular excesses. The main thing is that one year would be statistically similar to another one. This is because there are no long-period natural oscillations in the atmosphere itself.

The deep ocean changes the situation dramatically. Since it is inertial, it contains a lot of mechanisms of long-term fluctuations expressed in modifications of the surface temperature, generating large variations in heat exchange with atmosphere. The atmosphere reacts to those variations in a wide variety of ways. Therefore, in the real climate system, there is a huge spatial and temporal variability with the periods lasting decades. In most places on the Earth, the monotony of the weather is not boring. So, in addition to the burning of coal and gas, more powerful natural processes occur on the Earth. The understanding of the causes of a climate change by a man of today evokes a parallel with the Gulliver's behavior in the streets of London where upon returning from the land of Lilliputians he shouted to the Londoners passing by to step aside, lest he ran them over.

The true climate modeling should be based on the Creation scenario. It is assumed that at an initial stage, the atmosphere and ocean are at rest and have thermal uniformity. Other details need to be specified, but we omit them for brevity sake. We turn on the Sun... and then see what happens. There is a temperature difference between the equator and pole, the weather processes develop, while the upper layer of the ocean warms up and cools down in different places.

Finally, such a quasi-equilibrium stage would be achieved. However, I could swear that the structure of the deep ocean would be reproduced incorrectly: most likely it would be warmer than the real one. The reason for this is that the mechanism of forming the structure

of the deep ocean layers is very delicate and complex; besides, more powerful computers than the currently existing ones are required to reproduce it. If the correct global ocean structure is reproduced incorrectly, the Earth's climate will be also distorted. It follows that it would be quite irresponsible to rely on mathematical models to predict the long-term consequences.

Some evil tongues claim that the warming of a climate has occurred many times over thousands of years followed by an increase in carbon dioxide concentration (reminds the question "what is primary: chicken or egg?"). Without involvement of extraterrestrials it is difficult to explain those phenomena from the anthropogenic point of view.

The last line of defense of anthropogenic climate warming enthusiasts is based on a rate of warming. "The climate has never warmed so quickly before," - they say. We are talking about a time derivative of the global temperature. You can ask a counter-question: "Do you have enough data for such calculations?" "After all, we have only one single period of rapid warming illustrated by the data. The data available on the Earth climate history have an extremely low resolution and large errors, so comparison of time derivatives for the global temperature is impossible due to the obvious lack of data. One plant manager from the USSR stated that the refrigerator production plan for the current year was overfulfilled by 2 thousand percent." Formally he was right but he forgot to mention that the year before the plant produced just one refrigerator (and that one got broken down). In such difficult conditions the calculating of the time derivatives is not convincing.

Indeed, it is not necessary to burn a lot of coal. It stinks. Certainly there is no need to burn anything and throw it away as well. It seems ridiculous when someone sits in front of the TV with a bottle of beer, watches a global warming program and feels worried about the problem, while the following day goes to the nearest woodland park for a barbecue and leaves behind lots of plastic bottles and bags.

I would formulate the following conclusions:

1. The data on the globally averaged surface temperature show its growth over the past few decades.
2. A slow increase in surface temperature is accompanied by a significant increase in the spatial and temporal dispersion of temperature and other characteristics.
3. The dispersion of weather characteristics is a more significant and important characteristic of climate than the average annual temperature.
4. The mechanism of transformation of slow and uniform changes of the global temperature into the growth of weather characteristics dispersion is unclear.
5. The weather regime is closely related to distribution of the surface temperature in the oceans
6. The mechanism of formation of a three-dimensional structure of the ocean responsible for distribution of the surface temperature is known just qualitatively.
7. The adequate mathematical climate modeling has not been developed due to complexity of the ocean modeling.

If a ship sinks in a storm or the crops are destroyed by drought, the causes are the storm and drought but not carbon dioxide.